

REDEFINING MECHATRONICS TO FIT MODERN SYSTEMS AND TRENDS

Revision 3 volume 1

Masterclass | TT Mokgohloa
3 pages

05.06.2025

1. INTRODUCTION

If I was to define mechatronics It's not what many think, that it is a field that combines Mechanical, Electrical and Computer engineering to develop sophisticated machines and processes.

Mechatronics as per the evolution in history means the design, innovation of technologies and principles to optimise integrated machines, protect life and environment from preventable harms.

2: Curiosity

This is a story of the remarkable progress been made by mankind. From a simple curiosity came this wonderful exploration of matter together.

The real question is where is this curiosity leading us? (The innovation and engineering curiosity)?

3: Founding of logic system

George Boole was a born Mathematician, at age 20 he formed his own school where he taught Mathematics, a subject that he actually learnt on his own. He was such a genius and discovered that his algebra could also be applied in logic.

Boole's reasoning has led to applications of which he never dreamed—for example, telephone switching and electronic computers use binary digits and logical elements that rely on Boolean logic for their design and operation. ⁽¹⁾

4: Rossum's Universal Robot

Ironically the word ROBOT had a completely different meaning. Coined by a Czech Artist Josef Čapek to refer to hard labour. He was an older brother to Karel

Čapek, and both worked on numerous plays and art works. Around 1920s they introduced a play about a bad day at a factory which had employed Human-like machines.

Their father was a medical doctor at a textile factory. Although Karel only acknowledged that his father had an influence in his career, it is very likely that he and his brother's plays were in some sense attempting to prevent the injuries and illnesses people sustained at their father's work. Another play by Josef is called the insects' life, was yet again the idea of a machine mimicking a living creature. ⁽²⁾⁽³⁾

This was really the early stages of thinking of machines doing complicated human tasks and the dangers of being too reliant thereof. And mostly likely had inspired some of the films that were released after that, the likes of Robocop, The Matrix and so on.

5: First Robot used in production

George Devol, was a successful man in the 60s. And had dedicated his life to being an inventor. Among his inventions was a

“programmed article transfer” which he later sold to General motors to be used in a part of production process. ⁽⁴⁾

6: “Father of the PLC”

A 36 years old Richard Morley was working on a number of engineering proposals for the firm he founded, Bedford Associates engineering consulting firm. One of these projects that was due was a Machine control for General motors.

Morley woke up the 1st of January 1968 with a hangover and a reprieve from his company. For that split second an idea dawn on him, of a system that could be a solution to all his projects. He identified that thought these projects are different, they are in fact all having the same problem. Morley then wrote a 12 page document proposing what we now call the Programmable Logic Controller. ⁽⁵⁾

7: Birth of Mechatronics

Tetsuro Mori was employed as an engineer at Yaskawa in 1948 and became factory manager of small induction motors in 1957. The department was not performing well at the time due to the recession. The staff in this department was essentially at the verge of losing their job and Mori was haunted by this prospect.

One of his initial ideas of products was a machine called the “MO-CHIN-TROL” which means Motor machine control. He and his colleagues were attempting to integrate electric motor with mechanics and controls.

He has managed to actually save the production of small motors, also the contributing factor was that factories were starting divide the production process into automated modules. Instead of relying on one big electric motor, now more and smaller electric motor were being required.

As he proceeded to refine his system “MO-CHIN-TROL” and when he asked colleagues to adopt it for their production line and to evaluate it at an in-house exhibition, the director of marketing told him “We can go ahead with your system, but we can't call it ‘MO-CHIN-TROL’. It doesn't sound good and it sounds unsophisticated. Think of a cool name for it.” Then he came up with the “MECHA-TRONICS” from Mechanism and Electronics, and he filed it as a trademark at Yaskawa and was registered in 1971.

Originally, Mechatronics was created as a concept for new product development and as a philosophy for factory operation at Yaskawa. ⁽⁶⁾

8: First Mechatronics qualification

The term Mechatronics entered academics in the 90s. An Austrian university was first to introduce Mechatronics degree programme in the world. ⁽⁷⁾

9: Conclusion

My direct involvement dates back ten years ago (October 2014). Although my interest in the field dates back much earlier than that. At the time there were no campaign like today on coding robotics, 4ir etc. For me it was the passion for innovation and the realisation of the power this field has for the transformation how we live our daily lives as well as addressing our challenges and the environment.

In 2024 I started to take seriously the work that I have been doing and to begin publishing, as a result I published two books Digitalisation in Mechatronics and the recent one Mechatronics for the resolute. These books are technical and are really the expression of my industrial experience as a technician and trainer in an academic form.

A Mechatronic specialist's genius lies in their ability to design, assemble, wire, program, and commission automated systems. These systems include distributing, filling, packaging, sorting, robotics and more. They use logical,

efficient, cost-effective, primitive, and sustainable approach. Additionally, Mechatronic specialist fabricates and installs parts like brackets, keyways, shims that are needed for commissioning these automated systems.⁽⁸⁾

10: Acknowledgements

Osamu Ichikawa, Dr. Eng. Professor, Polytechnic University, Japan

11: Works Cited

1. **Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica & William L. Hosch.** biography/George-Boole. *www.britannica.com*. [Online] [Cited: 05 25, 2025.] <https://www.britannica.com/biography/George-Boole>.
2. **Wikipedia contributors.** Josef Čapek. *en.wikipedia.org*. [Online] 05 2, 2025. [Cited: 05 25, 2025.] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Josef_%C4%8Capek.
3. —. Karel Čapek. *en.wikipedia.org*. [Online] Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia, 05 2025, 16. [Cited: 05 25, 2025.] https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Karel_%C4%8Capek&oldid=1290715542.
4. —. George Devol. *en.wikipedia.org*. [Online] September 2, 2024. [Cited: May 25, 2025.] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/George_Devol.
5. **Contemporary Controls.** The Extension Volume 4 Issue 2 March-April 2003. *www.ccontrols.com*. [Online] March 2003. [Cited: 05 25, 2025.] <https://www.ccontrols.com/pdf/Extv4n2.pdf>.
6. *Philosophy of Mechatronics.* **Mori, Tetsuro.** 12, 1991, Vol. 57, pp. 1-5. doi.org/10.2493/jjspe.57.2089.
7. **Johannes Kepler University Linz.** The JKU's Milestones. *www.jku.at*. [Online] [Cited: 05 25, 2025.] <https://www.jku.at/en/the-jku/about-us/milestones/#:~:text=1990,academic%20degree%20program%20in%20Mechatronics..>
8. **Mokgohloa, TT.** *Mechatronics for the resolute*. Johannesburg : TT Mokgohloa, 2024.